

PREPARATION OF CORROSION INHIBITORS BASED ON SOME CARBO AND HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS

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Abstract

Our goal is to synthesize stable corrosion inhibitors to prevent corrosion, which is one of the most important problems of today. During the synthesis of these compounds, first of all, we need to ensure a more harmless, more convenient way and financially more profitable process of obtaining these compounds. To clarify the synthesis of corrosion inhibitors used to prevent corrosion and whether those inhibitors are useful, we must first examine what corrosion and corrosion inhibitors are. Information about them is given in a certain part of the article. Then, the most commonly used corrosion inhibitors and their synthesis were discussed.

Keywords: corrosion, corrosion inhibitors, heterocyclic compounds.

Introduction

Corrosion is a word of Latin origin and is taken from the word "Corrosion", which means to eat, to break up. Corrosion is the disintegration of metals as a

result of chemical, electrochemical, and biochemical effects. In short, we can say that corrosion is rusting of metals or their alloys under the influence of the environment.

Figure 1. Corrosion (rusting)

The interaction of moisture in the soil with copper or other metals can affect underground structures, cables, gas pipelines, oil pipelines, bridges, etc. has a major effect and this leads to the formation of rust. In order to reduce material costs, increase the operational reliability of equipment, and regulate procedures for protecting the metal stock, we must prevent the occurrence of corrosion. Although it is not possible to completely prevent corrosion, we can partially reduce its speed. The most convenient way to do this is to use corrosion inhibitors. Corrosion inhibitor is a chemical compound

that, when added to a liquid or gas, inhibits the formation of corrosion by affecting the metal compounds of the liquid. Inhibitor is derived from the Latin word "inhibeo", which means to stop the process, to slow down the process. According to their chemical nature, inhibitors are divided into 2 groups: inorganic and organic (including oils and acid inhibitors).

Inorganic corrosion inhibitors include phosphates, dichromates, molybdates, chromates, nitrites, polyphosphates, and silicates. Organic corrosion inhibitors include monoethanolamide, formaldehyde

Figure 2. The scheme of the inhibitor process using ammonium salts, amines, diethylamine, nitro compounds, etc. can be shown as an example. Corrosion inhibitors are adsorbed in the layer, act as a barrier by slowing down cathodic and anodic processes, and reduce corrosion.

Carbo and heterocyclic compounds both belong to the class of organic compounds and are cyclic, that is, compounds with a closed structure, and the main difference between them is that heterocyclic compounds have other heteroatoms (N, O, S, Se, P, Si) besides the carbon (C) atom in their structure. . The results of determining the activity of electrochemical and biological corrosion inhibitors based on some synthesized carbo and heterocyclic compounds are presented

METHODOLOGY OF THE EXPERIMENT

In this work, we evaluate the inhibitory effect of the simplest derivatives of heme dichloro cyclopropanes and 1,3-dioxolanes on secondary and tertiary amines, urethanes, and areas in different environments. Amines containing heme-dichlorocyclopropane or 1,3-dioxolane fragments 1-5 were obtained by alkylation of the corresponding amines with chloromethyl derivatives.

Table 1

Test results of steel 20 samples in 1M HCl solution (pH = 0) with the addition of synthesized compounds:

No Mixed	The concentration of a substance q/l	Corrosion rate, mm/year	Brake ratio	Degree of Protection %
Without an inhibitor	0,00	2,54	-	-
2	0,05	0,91	2,79	64
	0,10	0,55	4,62	78
3	0,05	0,83	3,06	67
	0,10	0,53	4,79	79
4	0,05	1,38	1,84	46
	0,10	1,11	2,29	56
13	0,05	1,36	1,87	47
	0,10	1,13	2,25	56

The corrosion rate of samples made of Steel 20 (GOST 1050-2013) is shown in table 1. These results were determined in non-inhibited and inhibited solutions of 1M HCl (pH = 0) using the Monicor-2M corrosion indicator. On the surface of the samples, traces of corrosion products with the presence of some compounds are noticeable, which indicates the formation of

a protective layer due to the adsorption of the investigated compounds.

To study the process of polarization of a metal surface in the presence of corrosion inhibitors, potentiodynamic studies of steel 20 samples in 1 M HCl (1 mol / l) solution were carried out at overvoltages of ± 200 mV. The potential of steel with compounds 2, 3, 4, and 13 is 0.1 g/l in the volume of the solution.

Table 2

parameters of polarization curves for 20 steel samples without compounds and with the addition of 0.1 g/l 2,3,4,13 compounds in 1M HCl solution:

№ Mixed	Tafel equation coefficients				Stationary potential, mV	Current density, A/m	Corrosion rate, mm/year	degree of protection, %
	a _a	b _a	AK	b _k				
Without an inhibitor	-0,280	-0,325	-0,398	-0,135	-335	2,14	2,483	-
2	-0,255	-0,470	-0,365	-0,048	-300	0,45	0,528	79
3	-0,310	-0,131	-0,340	-0,001	-335	0,43	0,497	80
4	-0,341	-0,105	-0,369	-0,004	-355	0,59	0,685	72
13	-0,303	-0,153	-0,346	-0,009	-321	0,87	1,007	60

To determine the ability of the substances to inhibit the corrosion process on the metal surface, studies were conducted at low overvoltages (± 10 mV from the value of the stationary potential). After extrapolating the polarization curves, the effectiveness of reducing the corrosion current density with the presence of the investigated compounds was calculated. Table 2 shows that compound No. 3 has the highest effectiveness in reducing the corrosion current on the surface of the steel sample at the same concentration in 1M HCl solution. It should be noted that compounds containing

2the,2-dimethylene dichlorocyclopropane group showed the highest result (more than 70%). Then, the adsorption activity of the synthesized compounds 2, 3, 4, 1and 3 was investigated by measuring the alternating current impedance using the potentiostat-impedance meter IPC-ProM/FRA-2 complex. We constructed impedance diagrams for samples of steel 20 in 1 M HCl solution at a mass concentration of compounds of 0.1 g/L. Impedance diagrams of substances 2, 3, 4, 1and 3 with a concentration of 0.1 g/l in 1M HCl are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Impedance diagrams for the investigated substances in 2, 3, 4, 13, 1M HCl.

The results of the convergence of experimental data are shown in Table 3. The degree of protection of the studied compounds (table 3) can be compared with the results of potentiodynamic studies, and the highest degree of protection corresponds to compound 3 and

reaches 80%. The presence of compounds increases the resistance to the corrosion process due to good adsorption of the synthesized compounds on the surface of the samples.

Table 3

Effectiveness of protection of steel in 1M HCl medium by addition of a series of synthesized compounds

Mixed	Polarization resistance $R_{corr}; R_{corr(inh)}$, OM	Degree of protection Z , %
Without inhibitor	82,8	-
Mixture 2	376,2	78
Mixture 3	397,8	79
Mixture 4	288,3	71
Mixture 13	174,2	52

Quantum-chemical indicators were calculated to correlate the inhibitory activity with the structural parameters of the compounds. Basic quantum-chemical parameters: q_N - nitrogen atom charge (Mulliken analysis), a.e.; Q_N - nitrogen atom charge (NBO analysis), a.e.; ϵ_{HOMO} - the energy of the upper molecular orbital, eB.; ϵ_{LUMO} - the energy of the lowest empty molecular orbital, eB.;

$$\mu = -(\epsilon_{HOMO} + \epsilon_{LUMO})/2 \quad \mu - \text{chemical potential, } \text{eB.}$$

$$\eta = (\epsilon_{HOMO} - \epsilon_{LUMO})/2 \quad \eta - \text{Pearson's hardness, } \text{eB.}$$

$$W = \mu^2/2 \eta \quad W - \text{global electrophilicity index, } \text{eB.}$$

From the results obtained from these gravimetric tests, it is clear that these synthesized compounds show high corrosion resistance. These compounds can be widely used in circulating water and wastewater of petrochemical enterprises for the protection of equipment made of carbon steel. The results obtained by testing the synthesized compounds according to GOST 9.502-82 are given in Table 4

Table 4

Results of testing the synthesized compounds in a model solution at different pH values

№ Əlaqələr	Bir maddənin konsentrasiyası q/l	Korroziya dərəcəsi, mm/il			Qoruma dərəcəsi%		
		Ph=0	Ph=4	Ph=7	Ph=0	pH=4	pH=7
Nəzarət	0,00	2.68	0.84	0.46	-	-	-
2	0,10	0,78	0.32	0.22	71	62	52
3	0,10	0,55	0.22	0.14	79	74	70
4	0,10	1.52	0.35	0.32	43	58	30
11	0,10	0.96	0.41	0.33	64	52	28

As a result of the research, it is known that it is possible to achieve the synthesis of successful corrosion inhibitors by making accurate calculations with the correct method and the following results can be achieved.

Based on the results of calculation and experimental methods, corrosion studies have shown that the synthesized carbo and heterocyclic compounds 2, 3, 4, 13 show a satisfactory degree of protection of more

than 50%, and the compound containing the 2,2-dimethyl-gem-dichlorocyclopropane moiety (3) helps reduce acid corrosion of carbon steel by almost 5 times.

Connections made by potentiodynamic methods showed that most of them polarize the research surface, which significantly reduces the corrosion current. High polarization resistance of compounds 2 and 3 were found, which indicates their high adsorption on the metal surface.

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FILTRATION STUDIES OF COMPOSITIONS ON CORE SAMPLES UNDER CONDITIONS CLOSE TO REAL DATA ON DEPOSITS OF WESTERN KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

This article discusses filtration studies of compositions on core samples under conditions close to real conditions for the deposit of JSC Embanefit Vostochny Moldabek. Core material of well No. 2205 was selected for the productive horizon M-II. A two-phase vertical filtration plant (LXRT-400T) was used to determine the filtration-capacitance properties (FCP) of reservoir rocks using a model of reservoir water and oil. This equipment is designed to study saturation profiles during filtration of two-phase flows in reservoir conditions in real time, representing average saturation as a function of core length and discrete points along the core as a function of time.

Keywords: Core, formation, horizon, well, research, filtration and capacitance properties (FCP).

The procedure for conducting research on a two-phase filtration unit with X-ray saturation control, the sequence and technique of conducting filtration experiments do not differ from the main provisions of existing methods and industry standards.

In the LXRT-400T system, the core holder is mounted in an upright position so that it can be scanned by a trolley mounted with an X-ray source and receiver system to monitor fluid saturation during the inflow test.

To determine the saturation profile of the core sample under study, the latter is placed in the core holder. Then the generator and the X-ray detector are switched on, which moves along the rail guides along the sample at a given speed and at certain intervals the detector registers the X-ray radiation that has passed through the sample. The signal received by the radiation detector is processed and output to the monitor in the form of a graph of the dependence of the intensity

of the transmitted radiation along the length of the sample. [1]

The water-oil saturation is calculated on the basis of Lambert's law, using the linearity of the semi-logarithmic dependence of the X-ray radiation, based on the base scanning points. [2]

In the oil-water system (with oil blocking):

$$S_{W_t} = \frac{\text{Log}(\text{Scan}_t) - \text{Log}(\text{Scan}_{K_o})}{\text{Log}(\text{Scan}_{K_w}) - \text{Log}(\text{Scan}_{K_o})} \quad (1)$$

where: S_{W_t} - current water saturation, fractions of units.;

Scan_t - the current intensity of the X-ray radiation transmitted through the sample;

Scan_{K_w} - x-ray intensity at 100% water saturation;

Scan_{K_o} - x-ray intensity at 100% oil saturation.

The determination of the displacement coefficient of oil and water was carried out in compliance with conditions as close as possible to reservoir conditions.